

EXPERIENCE OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES IN REGULATING CRYPTOCURRENCES**Shadieva S.A.**

Associate Professor of the Department of Civil and Private Law at the University of World Economy and Diplomacy, Candidate of Law
e-mail: s.shadiyeva@uwed.uz

Khudoyorova Nilufar**e-mail: nilufarkhudayarova@gmail.com**

Student of the University of World Economy and Diplomacy
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Annotation.

Countries or individual regions around the world have different attitudes and approaches to cryptocurrencies. Since digital currencies are almost a new field, their unified legal status has not been established, and there are no conflict norms or conventions. The article examines current issues of legal regulation of cryptocurrencies. It examines and analyzes the approaches of different countries to defining the legal nature of cryptocurrencies. The article is a comprehensive study of the legal status of cryptocurrencies and is intended for specialists in the field of law and finance, as well as a wide audience interested in new technologies.

Keywords: cryptocurrency, digital asset, legislation, investment, currency, legal regulation.

Introduction

Language is not a static entity but a dynamic and ever-evolving system that adapts to the changing needs of its speakers. English, one of the most widely spoken languages globally, exemplifies this dynamic nature through its vast and continuously expanding vocabulary. One of the primary mechanisms behind the growth of English vocabulary is word formation, a process that involves creating new words or altering existing ones to express novel ideas or concepts. The importance of word formation in the English language extends beyond mere lexical enrichment; it reflects the linguistic creativity of its users and the language's adaptability to cultural, technological, and social changes.

Word formation encompasses several processes, including affixation (the addition of prefixes and suffixes), compounding (the combination of two or more words), conversion (changing a word's grammatical category without altering its form), and blending (merging parts of words to form a new term). Each of these processes contributes to the evolution of English, allowing it to accommodate new inventions, cultural phenomena, and linguistic trends. As noted by Brown (2020, p. 45), "the flexibility of English in adopting and creating new words is one of its greatest strengths, enabling it to remain relevant across diverse contexts." [2, 87-96]

In today's globalized world, the ability to understand and utilize various word formation processes is essential for effective communication, especially in academic, professional, and technological fields. Additionally, knowledge of word formation processes can enhance language learning, particularly for non-native speakers, by providing insights into how new words are constructed and used. The study of word formation is not only of interest to linguists but also to educators, students, and language enthusiasts who seek to deepen their understanding of English vocabulary and its usage.

This article aims to explore the role of word formation in the English language by examining its various types, their linguistic significance, and their implications for language development. Through an in-depth analysis of these processes, we will highlight how word formation contributes to the richness and versatility of English, making it one of the most adaptable languages in the world.

Types of word formation in English

Word formation in English can be categorized into several processes, each with unique characteristics and functions. These processes are essential for generating new words and enriching the English lexicon.

Affixation is one of the most common methods of word formation in English. It involves adding prefixes or suffixes to a base word to create new words. For example, the prefix "un-" can be added to the word "happy" to form "unhappy," while the suffix "-ness" can transform "kind" into "kindness." According to Yule (2017), "affixation remains a highly productive method of creating new vocabulary in English, particularly in technical and scientific contexts." [6, 63]

Compounding involves combining two or more independent words to create a new term. This process is particularly productive in English, where words like "notebook," "airplane," and "toothbrush" are commonplace. The compounded words often reflect specific meanings that individual components cannot convey alone, thus expanding the expressive capacity of the language. Bauer (2016) points out that "compounding allows speakers to adapt existing vocabulary to new contexts, reflecting the changing realities of modern life" [1, 88]

Conversion, also known as zero derivation, is the process of changing a word's grammatical category without altering its form. For instance, the noun "email" can be converted into a verb as in "to email someone." This process is particularly useful in modern English, where the demand for linguistic economy often leads to the multifunctional use of words. As stated by Plag (2018), "conversion is a testament to the flexibility of English, allowing words to adapt quickly to different grammatical functions" [5, 92].

Blending merges parts of two or more words to form a new term, often capturing elements of each original word. Examples include "brunch" (from "breakfast" and "lunch") and "smog" (from "smoke" and "fog"). This process is particularly prevalent in popular culture and media, where catchy, memorable terms are valued. According to Brown (2020), blending "illustrates the creative aspect of word formation, often resulting in words that become part of everyday usage" [2, 45].

Clipping involves shortening longer words without changing their meaning, such as "ad" for "advertisement" or "gym" for "gymnasium." This process is driven by the need for brevity in communication, particularly in informal contexts. As noted by Katamba (2019), "clipping is a reflection of linguistic efficiency, catering to the fast-paced nature of modern communication" [3, 77].

The linguistic and social impact of word formation

The processes of word formation are not just linguistic phenomena but are also reflective of social and cultural trends. The rise of digital communication, social media, and technological innovations has led to the rapid creation of new words, many of which are formed through the processes discussed above. For instance, terms like "selfie," "hashtag,"

and "cyberbullying" have emerged in response to digital culture, illustrating how word formation can respond to societal changes.

Furthermore, word formation processes play a significant role in language learning. Non-native English speakers can benefit from understanding how new words are formed, as it helps in expanding their vocabulary and improving their comprehension of complex texts. According to Nation (2020), "awareness of word formation patterns can greatly enhance vocabulary acquisition, providing learners with strategies to decode unfamiliar terms" [4, 102].

Conclusion.

Word formation is a vital aspect of the English language, contributing to its growth, adaptability, and richness. The processes of affixation, compounding, conversion, blending, and clipping are not only essential for the development of new vocabulary but also reflect the language's responsiveness to cultural, technological, and social changes. As English continues to evolve, the study of word formation remains crucial for linguists, educators, and language learners alike.

The ongoing creation of new words in response to changing societal needs demonstrates the flexibility and resilience of English. As language continues to adapt to new realities, the processes of word formation will remain central to its evolution. Thus, understanding these processes is not only a matter of linguistic curiosity but also a practical tool for mastering the complexities of the English language.

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